

AI4

Implementation plan

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1. INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve the project objectives, it is necessary to organize and coordinate the development efforts and ensure their alignment with the user requirements. For these reasons, an implementation plan is essential. This plan pertains to the components that will be developed and released as part of Work Package 4, “Next generation AI PaaS”. WP4 is responsible for implementing the necessary solutions to provision a distributed computing platform that is secure and efficient, designed to enable the training and inference of AI models across the EOSC continuum. The Platform will enable dynamic deployment of AI services and applications across multiple back-ends, including access to specialized hardware like GPUs. Users will be able to bring their own computing and storage resources and add them to the platform. The platform will support advanced learning scenarios, provide computational support to expose trained models from the AI4EOSC Exchange as scalable inference endpoints, and deliver interactive development environments for easy user access. On top of this platform, Work Package 5 “Experiment centric AI services” will implement and deliver the AI4EOSC software as a service layer (see Deliverable 5.1 for implementation details).

The purpose of this implementation plan is to enable the smooth execution of the initial project plan by defining the roadmap and the technologies that will be utilized during each phase of the AI4EOSC project. In order to ensure effective implementation, this document will outline the project objectives and provide a timeline of the tasks required for the successful implementation of each WP4 component. By following this well-crafted implementation strategy, the project team will be better positioned to achieve their goals and deliver high-quality outcomes within the designated timeframe.

We have been able to gain valuable insights by closely aligning with Work Package 3 “*Architecture co-design and portfolio of services*”, responsible for eliciting the user requirements and developing the AI4EOSC architecture, which will serve as the foundation for the activities carried out by WP4 and WP5. Specifically, Deliverable 3.1 [1] provides a comprehensive overview of existing frameworks pertaining to advanced learning and MLOps, while Deliverable 3.2 [2] outlines the initial architecture specifications for the AI4EOSC platform. This document details the technologies that will be utilised throughout the project's lifecycle to meet the user requirements. By taking into account the information presented in these deliverables, we can ensure that the project is carried out in a manner that is aligned with our goals and objectives.

This deliverable presents a detailed timeline outlining the steps for AI4EOSC Release 1, scheduled for M18, as well as for AI4EOSC Release 2, expected to be completed by the end of M33. While this plan serves as a starting point for project planning, it is subject to modification as the components and corresponding tasks continue to evolve during the course of the project. User feedback collected in WP6 will be taken into account to ensure that the project is carried out in alignment with the project's

objectives. Our agile and flexible approach will enable us to deliver both releases efficiently and effectively, achieving the desired outcomes.

DOCUMENT STRUCTURE AND NOTATION

After the introduction, in section 2, an initial design is described according to the initial architecture specification proposed by D3.2 - "*Initial high-level architecture specification*" [2]. A high-level overview of the main components of the platform as well as how they will work is also explained to understand the different approaches of the project. The following sections 3 and 4 define the technologies used for implementing each of the components, together with a brief description of how each of them can fit with each component's purpose.

Sections 5 and 6 present the roadmap planned for the AI4EOSC releases 1 and 2: each component's roadmap is detailed with an explanation of the corresponding tasks that will be carried out throughout the project, taking into account the inputs from the user requirements.

GOAL AND SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT

The main goal of the AI4EOSC project is to deliver an enhanced set of services for the development and deployment of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Deep Learning (AI/ML/DL) models and applications in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) context. The AI4EOSC platform, as an evolution of the DEEP-Hybrid-Datacloud platform (DEEP-HDC) [3], will be focused on enhancing the current DEEP services and will make use of advanced new features such as distributed, split, and federated learning, provenance metadata, event-driven data processing technologies, or the provisioning of AI/ML/DL services based on serverless computing.

The project will place a special emphasis on ensuring that all the research results and sub-products (data, models, metadata, publications, etc.) adhere to the FAIR and research principles.

The vision of the AI4EOSC project is to increase the service offer in the EU landscape by expanding the EOSC ecosystem to support the effective usage of state-of-the-art AI techniques by the research community.

In this regard, this document provides a description and the implementation plans of the frameworks and technologies that compose the *Next Generation AI Platform* for the correct development of the AI4EOSC 1 and AI4EOSC 2 releases. By following this roadmap, we can ensure that the project is executed in a manner that aligns with the project's objectives, delivering high-quality outcomes that meet the needs of the users.

2. SYSTEM DESIGN

This section describes the design of the software platform. It refers to the “Initial high-level architecture specification” deliverable (D3.2 [2]) for the architecture, components, and relationships between the different components. It also provides a high-level view of how the platform will work and how it will support the requirements outlined in WP6.

As a general overview, without entering into details of each component, the project will deliver the *AI4EOSC platform* that aims to enhance a set of services for the development of AI/ML/DL models and applications in the EOSC context. Taking this as reference, the AI4EOSC platform, based on the DEEP-HDC platform, will evolve some of the DEEP services, such as the resource computing orchestration, the cluster manager, the training dashboard, and the interactive environment, and will integrate new tools for the validation of the models, the federated learning, and the provision of AI/ML/DL services based on serverless computing. These goals will drive the implementation or evolution of the components described below.

Deliverable 3.2 provides a comprehensive description of the AI4EOSC system architecture, including detailed diagrams of each service and the relationships between components. The diagrams included in Deliverable 3.2 have been created following the C4 model, which is a methodology for designing software architecture diagrams. This model allows for a clear and concise representation of the system architecture, providing a common language for communicating design decisions and facilitating collaboration among team members. For the purposes of this document, only the high-level architecture diagram of AI4EOSC has been included for reference (Figure 1) in order to show how the services and components are organized based on their purpose within the system.

Table 1 summarizes the components of the final AI4EOSC platform that are relevant for WP4.

[System Landscape] AI4EOSC
Wednesday, 14 March 2024 10:52:00 AM CET (Central European Standard Time)

Figure 1: AI4EOSC platform diagram following the C4 model

Group	Component
PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning	PaaS Dashboard
	PaaS Orchestrator
	Infrastructure Manager
	Federated Service Catalogue
	Monitoring and Metering System
	Cloud Provider Ranker
AI4EOSC Training	Workload Management System
	Federated Learning Server
	Interactive Development Environment
AI-as-a-Service Framework	OSCAR
	FaaS Supervisor

Table 1: AI4EOSC components that will be implemented and delivered as part of WP4 "Next generation AI PaaS"

The **PaaS Orchestration and provisioning components** are mainly responsible for the provisioning of computing resources for the deployment of the virtual environments where the processing tasks (both training and inference workloads) will be executed. Within this context, the **PaaS Orchestrator** [4], based on the solutions initially developed during the INDIGO Datacloud project [5], will be mainly in charge of finding the appropriate resources, including specialised hardware like GPUs, for deployment requests. The Orchestrator must have the ability to identify available resources with the required specifications and allocate them accordingly, while ensuring optimal utilization of the available resources. Currently, the PaaS Orchestrator is integrated with the **Infrastructure Manager (IM)** [6] service for the provisioning and configuration of cloud resources (virtual machines, block storage, networks, etc.) through TOSCA templates and Ansible recipes following an Infrastructure as Code (IaC) methodology. Within AI4EOSC the PaaS Orchestration system will be used to allow the automatic provisioning of the training and serverless facilities needed to run the AI/ML/DL workloads.

The training facilities will be implemented through a **Workload Management System**, which operates as a server-client cluster. This system will efficiently manage the distribution of workloads across multiple nodes, ensuring that the computational resources are utilized effectively and that the training process is completed in a timely manner. The user application will be encapsulated in containers based on Docker technology to ease the correct deployment inside the selected Compute client.

Federated learning (FL) is a crucial aspect that needs to be addressed to meet the requirements of the use-cases supported by the AI4EOSC project, which include scenarios where data is not equally distributed, not accessible, or privacy concerns prevent centralized learning. Federated Learning is a data decentralization privacy-preserving technique used to perform machine or deep learning in a secure way [8]. The AI4EOSC **Federated Learning Training service** aims to allow the collaboration of different entities (clients) which have data that can be used for performing a common task but cannot be shared among them due to technical or privacy concerns. With FL we can ensure that data does not leave the machines assigned to each client, even for training the model. In AI4EOSC platform, this service will be integrated with the Workload Management System in order to securely orchestrate the communication between the server and the different clients.

Interactive environments will be made available for the users to interact with the AI module's code and functionalities. These environments, which will be based on modern development platforms and tools such as JupyterLab [7], are designed to enable quick prototyping and the development of applications with limited resource access. The goal is to provide a familiar entry path for developers before they move on to the training, evaluation, and testing phases carried out at scale.

In relation to the inference capabilities, we will implement the **AI as a Service framework** to offer the AI/ML/DL models as a service using an event-driven serverless approach. It will be based on the **OSCAR** platform [8] for data-processing

applications, which provides the ability to run container-based applications and execute them in response to inference requests. For this, the **FaaS supervisor** provides the ability to perform data stages from the user's request into the container sandbox to perform the inference process, and storing the output data in the supported object-storage systems. The AI as a Service system will also include the **AI4Compose** component, responsible for supporting Composite AI by allowing the workflow composition of multiple inference requests to different AI models. This component will be developed and released as part of WP5 and therefore its details can be found in the *WP5 Implementation Plan* (Deliverable 5.1).

3. TECHNOLOGY STACK

In the previous section, Table 1 lists the group of services and components that are part of the AI4EOSC platform and that will be developed in WP4. In the following section, we present a concise overview of the technologies chosen for each of those components. Taking into account the evolution of the technologies, this overview should be seen as a starting point, and the tools could be adapted in order to accomplish the requirements during the lifetime of the project.

3.1 PaaS ORCHESTRATION AND PROVISIONING

- **PaaS Orchestrator**: built with Java technologies and on the open-source Workflow Manager “Flowable” [9], the Orchestrator allows federating heterogeneous resource providers and orchestrate the deployment of TOSCA templates, selecting the best provider according to criteria like the data location, the SLA and monitoring information. It provides a set of APIs to create, monitor and manage the deployments.
- **PaaS Dashboard** [10]: it's a Flask [11] application with a SQL database that enables users to interact easily with the services of the PaaS, particularly the Orchestrator, to create TOSCA-based deployments. The dashboard provides a user-friendly interface for managing and monitoring deployments.
- **Infrastructure Manager** [6]: it's a Python tool designed to simplify the access and usability of IaaS clouds for scientific applications. It automates the selection, deployment, configuration, monitoring, and update of virtual appliances. It supports APIs from various cloud platforms, provides a contextualization system for installing and configuring user-required applications, and offers multiple access methods including a web-based GUI, a XML-RPC API, a REST API, and a command-line application.
- **Federated Service Catalogue**: this component will be introduced in AI4EOSC to collect and publish information about the federated providers, their services and resources availability. Automatic and dynamic registration of new providers/resources will be supported in order to allow user

communities to bring their own computing and storage resources and add them to the AI4EOSC platform for training and inference.

- **Monitoring and Metering System:** this component will be used in AI4EOSC to collect metrics from the federated providers in order to monitor their status and provide the Orchestrator with useful information for selecting the optimal deployment path.
- **Cloud Provider Ranker** [12]: this is a Java application built on top of the open-source Rule Engine “Drools” [13] that is able to compute a rank for each federated provider considering parameters like the resources quota provided to the users groups, and the monitoring information (services availability, performance metrics).

3.2 AI4EOSC TRAINING

- **Workload Management System:** we will leverage [Hashicorp Nomad](#) [14] which aims to orchestrate applications, similar to Kubernetes [15]. This service acts as a scheduler cluster manager that automates the orchestration of the end-user applications in the compute resources. Nomad was designed to handle multi-datacenter and multi-region deployments, an interesting feature according to the distributed and federated learning principles that AI4EOSC projects want to achieve. Nomad will be integrated with other solutions of the Hashicorp ecosystem like [Consul](#) [16] for the discovery and secure connectivity between an infrastructure and across multi-cloud environments. As load balancer, we will use [Traefik Proxy](#) [17].
- **Interactive development Environment:** To allow a friendly developing experience for users, we plan to offer [JupyterHub](#) [18] environments managed via [Jupyter Enterprise Gateway](#) [19], similar to Google Colab [20]. As users develop more complex code, they might need a proper IDE, and for this we plan to explore making available environments with [Visual Studio Code](#) [21], similar to Github Codespaces [22].

3.3 AI AS A SERVICE FRAMEWORK

The implementation of the AI as a Service framework will be based on the open-source OSCAR [23] serverless computing platform for data-processing applications. Users upload files to an object-storage system (provided for example by MinIO [24]) and this automatically triggers the execution of parallel invocations to a function (OSCAR service) responsible for processing each file. Output files are delivered into an output bucket for the convenience of the user. A user-provided shell script is executed inside the container run from the user-defined Docker image to achieve the right execution environment for the application. Synchronous invocations, required for short-lived inference requests, are handled via KNative [25]. Using the [Infrastructure Manager](#) [6], OSCAR can be deployed over an elastic [Kubernetes](#) [15] cluster dynamically provisioned on any supported Cloud provider.

For clusters of low-powered devices such as Raspberry Pis, OSCAR can be deployed over a minimalistic Kubernetes distribution such as K3s [26].

Figure 2: Architecture of the OSCAR platform.

The following components are part of the AI as a Service:

- **Kubernetes API:** The Kubernetes API is used to manage services, create jobs and retrieve logs regarding the status of a service execution.
- **FaaS supervisor:** Component in charge of managing the data stage from the object storage that triggered the event into the container-based processing environment. It also uploads the output data to the supported external storage providers.
- **MinIO:** An open-source high-performance object storage which provides an API compatible with that of Amazon S3. The result of a function execution can also be stored on different storage providers such as Amazon S3, or Onedata [27].
- **OSCAR Manager:** Provides the API-based entry point to the platform. The interaction with the manager can be through either a Web-based GUI [28], a CLI (command-line interface) [29], a REST API based on the OpenAPI specification [30], or a Python-based library [31], to facilitate integration with Python-based environments, such as Jupyter Notebooks.
- **Knative** [25]: an open-source enterprise-level solution to build serverless and event-driven applications. Knative is used to provide a scalable solution to the execution of synchronous invocation requests.

3.4. FEDERATED TRAINING

The deliverable “D3.1 State-of-the-art landscaping and initial platform requirements specification” describes the existing and most promising open source MLOps and Federated Learning frameworks [8]. This initial implementation plan will not define which framework will be finally implemented because an in-depth evaluation of the different frameworks will be needed in the first release and initial stages of the second release.

3.5. IDENTITY AND ACCESS MANAGEMENT

When building a platform, managing user access is crucial. The integration with OAuth2 external providers such as EGI Check-In (Keycloak instance) [32] or DEEP-based Identity and Access Management (IAM) [33] system will enable the user federation authentication and authorization to allow the user access from various institutions. A new Virtual Organization (VO) called “**vo.ai4eosc.eu**”, has been created and is being enabled for the EOSC users as well as the enrolled users coming from other institutions.

4. SERVICES AND RESOURCES FOR DEVELOPMENT

This section provides information on how the development environment will be set up. It explains the tools and services that will be used to develop, test, and deploy the platform (these should be provided by Deliverable 7.1 - “*Initial plan for Quality Assurance and data FAIRness*” [34]). It also provides information on how developers will access the environment and what resources they will need to get started. The relationship between the development environment with the requirements DB [35] is shown below in table 2.

Requirement	Component	Description
UC1.Req006 Perform automated code testing UC1.Req008 Streamline service releases through CI/CD UC1.Req015 UC2.Req16 UC3.Req13 Check/Run data, software and user application (service) quality	CI/CD tools (Jenkins)	Code testing (via flake8 and tox) is already implemented in the CI/CD pipeline, but we will keep improving the services offered.

UC1.Req014 UC2.Req08 UC3.Req09 Containerise the application(s)	CI/CD tools (Jenkins)	The CI/CD pipeline will be in charge of automatically containerizing the applications, but improvements will keep being made to hide technicalities from users.
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Table 2: CI/CD requirements coverage

The Deliverable D7.1 [34] contains a brief description of the infrastructure to be used for development. The underlying infrastructure consists of cloud resources from the EGI Fedcloud, including IFCA/CSIC, IISAS, INCD, and INFN. These providers are based on OpenStack software [36] and, as anticipated in the previous section, they are supporting the newly created Virtual Organization **vo.ai4eosc.eu** as a means of providing resources for the project.

Given the above description, all the services and platforms developed by the project will be deployed on those cloud providers. Additionally, since the providers have access to specialized hardware resources such as GPUs, these resources will be provided or made accessible to both the development and testing teams as well as the user communities.

Cloud resources are provided as needed for the development of the individual components of the platform. This can be coordinated by task T7.3 or provided by the development team itself.

The PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning system can be used to deploy specific services for integration and testing during development of the AI4EOSC platform. By doing this, a development environment that closely resembles a production environment can be created. This allows for thorough testing of individual components or services with the other services of the platform.

The development environment is well-suited to support a complete CI/CD(D) Jenkins [37] pipeline. This pipeline begins with all **Continuous Integration** checks, including style checking, unit testing, and functional testing. It then moves to **Continuous Delivery**, where artifacts such as Docker images are built and published in public repositories. Finally, it concludes with **Continuous Deployment**, where the artifacts are deployed and configured. Additional tests, such as API tests and integration tests, can then be performed.

In Deliverable D7.1 [34], Section 3.1 contains the list of services and tools for the development, while Section 4 describes the infrastructure for software development and integration.

5. AI4EOSC 1 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

This section outlines the implementation plan for the first major release of the software platform, AI4EOSC 1. It includes details on the priorities, requirements coverage and the roadmap for each core component. This section provides a detailed view of what will be done during the first phase of the implementation and how it will be done.

PRIORITIES

Following the planning of the project, the first major release AI4EOSC will be published by the end of M18 (March 2024). Minor beta versions of the platform will be released for the testing phase of the use case requirements. The following activities must be defined in this first version to achieve the use case requirements described below.

The PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning priorities

The following items are the main priorities for the PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning components:

- remove the dependency from legacy and unmaintained services/components;
- support the automatic deployment of the core services of the AI4EOSC platform so that they can be easily deployed by external resource providers. This will be achieved by implementing and providing recipes like TOSCA templates, Ansible roles, docker images, etc.;
- provide the ability to integrate new computing and storage resources to the PaaS platform in an easy way with almost no manual steps.

AI as a Service priorities

These are the priorities identified for the AI as a Service components:

- provide easy-to-use approaches to facilitate the deployment of the models from the AI4EOSC Dashboard in OSCAR clusters, considering different user profiles and different access mechanisms (GUI, CLI);
- implement the required support in the FaaS supervisor to interact with the object storage systems identified and adopted in the project (e.g. NextCloud);
- integrate support for visual user interfaces crafted for the specific AI models, based on Gradio [38] or similar tools;
- implement libraries to facilitate the programmatic deployment of models from the DEEP Open Catalog in OSCAR cluster, from different programming languages, with a special focus on Python;

- develop strategies to efficiently pre-load the AI models' Docker images in the underlying computing platform to mitigate the start-up times for the first inference requests.

The AI4EOSC training priorities

The following list presents the priorities based on their criticality and impact on the project's objectives:

- Implementation of the Workload Management System based on Nomad + Consul, removing the legacy Apache Mesos [39] cluster manager inherited from DEEP;
- setting up the new Integrated Development Environment;
- evaluate Federated Learning frameworks in order to define a well-designed workflow that fits with the requirements.

REQUIREMENTS COVERAGE

For a more manageable view, the requirements coverage table has been broken down into sub-tables in the Roadmap sections below.

The tables introduce all requirements collected by WP6 in [35] that are planned to be covered in the **first release** of the AI4EOSC platform. The column "Component" defines the group of components which should carry out that requirement. In addition, a brief explanation of each procedure is included.

TIMELINE AI4EOSC 1

This section provides a graphical timeline showing when the components of the AI4EOSC Release 1 [M1 - M18] will be implemented. This timeline summarizes the roadmap explained in the sections below, adding a final stage needed for testing.

Figure 3: Timeline of actions for the first AI4EOSC release. Green cells indicate the time range from development to deployment. All components will still be maintained and improved after deployment, though not shown in the Table to avoid clutter.

AI4EOSC 1 ROADMAP

1. PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning Roadmap

Requirement	Component	Description
UC1.Req001 Provision/customize the required computing resources to optimize the AI/ML/DL training process	PaaS Orchestrator PaaS Dashboard Infrastructure Manager	Proper selection of computing resources must be done in order to speed up the AI/ML training process. *Appropriate computing resources are available (hardware is available): 32GB GPUs, enough storage (see UC3.E01.US01) (c) *Computing resources information is easily available for model developers (m) *Appropriate computing resources can be requested/selected by a user via the Dashboard or CLI: number of CPUs, amount of storage, TYPE OF GPU (e.g. GPU memory is important!), Number of GPUs (c) *The platform offers development environment, e.g. JupyterLab, VSCode which is also integrated with other

		components of the platform and allows direct access to e.g. GPUs (c)
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Table 3: AI4EOSC-1 Roadmap: PaaS orchestration requirements coverage

1.1. PaaS Orchestrator

For the first release AI4EOSC-1, the following implementation activities will be carried out:

Integration with the new services, Federated Service Catalog and Monitoring & Metering System

The PaaS Orchestrator will be extended to be able to get the needed information from the Federated Services Catalogue (which will replace CMDB as described later), SLAM, the newly implemented Monitoring System. The proper data structures and methods will be designed to efficiently retrieve the information needed from the new services while also maintaining compatibility with the existing functionality of the Orchestrator.

Support for automatic deployment of the Workload Management System (Nomad)

The automatic deployment of the core components of the Workload Management System, i.e. Nomad and Consul, will be implemented by means of a TOSCA template and Ansible role. The TOSCA template provides a standardized blueprint for the deployment of Nomad and Consul, while the Ansible roles automate the configuration of the infrastructure provisioned through the Infrastructure Manager. This ensures that the deployment process is fast, reliable, and repeatable, reducing the risk of errors and minimizing the time and effort required for manual deployment.

Support for automatic deployment of the OSCAR service

As in the previous case, we will add the possibility to deploy the OSCAR service through the PaaS Orchestrator by means of a TOSCA template and Ansible roles. The Orchestrator will make use of the Infrastructure Manager to provision and configure the infrastructure.

1.2. Infrastructure Manager

Improved OSCAR service deployment

Currently, IM supports the management of OSCAR services with a set of basic features. More advanced features such as GPU support or any other new features added to the definition of OSCAR services will be added not only in TOSCA (adding/updating the corresponding custom types) but also adding the support in the IM runtime.

Support for infrastructure names defined by users

To enhance the user's experience interacting with the IM service, new metadata "infrastructure name" will be added, not only in RADL (the native IM infrastructure description language) but also in TOSCA, enabling the user to interact with the IM using the infrastructure name in addition to the traditional internal generated UID.

Advanced service usage extraction

New methods to extract the IM service usage extraction will be made enabling the service administration to get a fine grain detail of the number of users, deployments, VMs launched, etc.

Add support to Ansible collections

Currently, IM supports the specification of Ansible roles to be used in the recipes used in the infrastructure's contextualization. The support for collections will enable the Ansible roles/recipes developers to use any Ansible collection available in the Ansible Galaxy service in their playbooks, leaving the installation of the collections to the IM contextualization agent.

1.3. Federated Service Catalogue

This is a new component that will be designed and implemented in order to replace the legacy Configuration Management Database (CMDB) [40] implemented during the INDIGO-Datacloud project. The main function of the CMDB is to store and manage the description of providers and their services (compute and storage) and resources, including virtual machine images, flavors, networks, etc. Currently, the backend of the service is based on a NoSQL database (CouchDB [41]) on top of which a schema is partially implemented using a custom npm package called *schema-couch-roles* [42] that is no longer maintained (the last version 0.0.5 was published 6 years ago). The frontend is implemented by a Java Spring Boot Application that provides simple APIs to perform CRUD operations on the records stored in the Database. Apart from a minor update in the schema made in late 2019, the application has not been updated in the last 6 years and supports an old and vulnerable version of CouchDB.

Given the importance of this component for the overall functioning of the PaaS layer, it has been decided to replace the old, unmaintained components with new open-source solutions. The new service will need to be scalable, reliable, and secure, with a focus on data accuracy and consistency. This will involve implementing robust data validation and error handling mechanisms, as well as implementing appropriate security measures such as authentication and access control.

Design and implementation of the core services

A variety of technologies can be used. We are evaluating:

1) Solution based on Graph databases, a newer type of database that is specifically designed to manage relationships between entities. They are ideal for use cases where the relationships between data entities are complex or highly interconnected. To get started with a graph database, it is important to define a clear data model

that captures the entities and relationships that are important to the use case. This might involve defining node and edge types, and specifying the properties and metadata that are associated with each type. For implementing the frontend popular frameworks like Flask [11] and Angular [43] or React [44] can be used to build the API and the user interfaces.

2) Solution based on OpenSearch [45], a powerful search engine that is widely used for indexing, searching, and analyzing large volumes of data. It provides a robust and scalable platform for building search-based applications and has a wide range of features and capabilities that make it a popular choice for many use cases. Concerning the data, OpenSearch can be used with a schema by defining an index mapping that specifies the data types and fields that are used to store the data. This can help ensure consistency and accuracy in the data, as well as improve performance by optimizing the storage and indexing of the data. Since the OpenSearch APIs are powerful but complex, GraphQL [46] can be used for building a consistent and predictable API. GraphQL, in fact, is a query language and runtime for APIs that allows clients to define the structure of the data that they need, and provides a single endpoint for retrieving the data. It can be used to query OpenSearch by defining a GraphQL schema that maps to the OpenSearch index mapping, and defining resolvers that map the GraphQL queries to OpenSearch queries. By using OpenSearch with a schema and GraphQL for querying, it is possible to combine the powerful indexing and search capabilities of OpenSearch with the flexibility and ease of use of GraphQL.

Design and implementation of the information discovery mechanism

Defining the mechanisms that populate the Catalogue is an important aspect of the system's design. We can use a combination of automated discovery and manual input.

Automated discovery agents can be run locally or remotely (on the providers) in order to collect information about the resources and services available in their respective domains and register new information in the Catalogue. Running the discovery agents centrally can simplify the management and monitoring of the agents themselves, as they can be centrally deployed, configured, and monitored.

On the other hand, running the agents locally to the providers can simplify the data collection process in cases of specific (restrictive) access constraints (e.g. absence of cloud interfaces, need to avoid external service accounts, etc.). To add a new provider to the Catalogue, the infrastructure administrator can deploy an instance of the discovery agent in their infrastructure, and configure it to push information about their resources to the Catalogue service. The Catalogue service can then automatically discover the new provider and add it to its inventory.

A hybrid approach can be used, where some agents are run centrally and others are run locally. This can help to balance the trade-offs between central management and local data collection.

Manual input can be used to manually enter data about resources that are not automatically discovered, such as resources that are not directly connected to the network or resources that are not compatible with the discovery agents. For example, manual input can be used to add data about legacy systems or resources that are not supported by automated discovery agents.

Another mechanism for populating the Catalog is by integrating with other systems. Integration with other systems, such as the Monitoring & Metering system (see next section), can provide additional data about resources, their relationships, and their dependencies, allowing the Catalog to be more complete and up-to-date.

1.4. Monitoring & Metering System

This service will replace the “Monitoring Pillar” developed during the INDIGO-DataCloud project. As in the case of the previous service (CMDB), the INDIGO Monitoring framework [47] is based on legacy and no longer maintained code, in particular: the Zabbix Wrapper, a Java application that provides REST APIs for getting metrics from the Zabbix Server (where the metrics are collected and stored) by wrapping Zabbix's JSON-RPC 2.0 API, and a set of Zabbix probes written in Java and used to perform monitoring checks on Openstack clouds, Mesos, QCG, etc. The framework is more cumbersome than necessary, making it difficult to maintain. Therefore, we have decided to re-design and implement the monitoring system, exploiting well-known open-source solutions like Prometheus [48] that support collecting metrics from different sources and can handle large amounts of data efficiently. It was designed to work in cloud and distributed environments and is used by many large companies for monitoring their systems. Moreover, Prometheus supports the OpenMetrics standard [49], which is an open, vendor-neutral standard for exposing metrics over HTTP, favoring interoperability with other systems. Prometheus also includes a powerful and adaptable query API for retrieving and manipulating metrics data in a variety of ways and a wide range of exporters, which are software components that extract metrics data from various sources (they act as intermediaries between the data source and Prometheus, translating the data into a format that can be understood by Prometheus).

The new service will collect data about the health status, the performances of the federated services (compute and storage), and the resources' availability. These data will be collected from the different providers through dedicated exporters if the monitored services do not provide OpenMetrics-compliant endpoints. Aggregated metrics will be sent to the Federated Service Catalog in order to complete the services information.

For the first release AI4EOSC-1, the following activities will be completed:

- identify the metrics to be collected, taking into account those that are important for the orchestrator scheduling algorithm;
- collect the metrics from the different providers, implementing the needed agents and tools;
- aggregate the metrics based on the different providers;

- expose the metrics via REST APIs, which can return JSON-formatted data that can be easily consumed by applications and other services.

1.5. Cloud Provider Ranker

The Cloud Provider Ranker [12] is the PaaS Orchestration system component in charge of assigning a rank to each of the candidate federated providers that can be used to deploy the user application. Currently, the information used by the ranking algorithm is the monitoring information collected from the different providers and the static initial quotas of resources (cores, ram, disk space, etc.) reserved for the different user groups.

The following implementation activities are foreseen for the first release:

Improve the ranking algorithm

The ranking algorithm will be extended in order to take into account further information, in particular the dynamic resource availability at the different providers. This will aid in improving the scheduling capabilities of the PaaS orchestrator and increasing the performance of the deployment workflow (reducing failures due to exceeded quotas, which necessitate the automatic rescheduling of the request, resulting in delay).

Change the REST API

The change in the input information will be reflected in the API specification, which will be adapted accordingly.

2. AI as a Service Roadmap

The AI as a Service component is responsible for exposing the trained AI/ML models to be used for efficient and scalable inference on top of the computing infrastructure provisioned for the project.

The results of the requirements gathering process, reported in Deliverable D6.1 “Analysis of user applications, collections of requirements” identified several requirements that need to be supported by the AI as a Service component.

Requirement	Component	Description
UC1.Req004 Programmatically retrieve prediction information from Model Inference	OSCAR Manager	During experimentation tools used are: R, Matlab, Statistica, Python, MS Excel, Jupyter notebooks. For tracking different versions some experience with DVC. DL frameworks used are: Tensorflow and PyTorch.
UC1.Req007 Deploy AI/ML/DL model inference as	OSCAR Manager, FaaS Supervisor	The model inference process requires several steps to be executed: (current data must be preprocessed by

<p>a service</p> <p>UC2.Req11 Deploying model for real-time prediction</p> <p>UC3.Req05 Analyse end user images to identify potential problems (e.g. leaks underground, heat bridges)</p>		<p>underlying basic extrapolation algorithms before entering inference).</p> <p>Generated models are hosted on the platform.</p> <p>An interface is provided for users or systems to send data to the model and receive the model's predictions or inferences.</p>
<p>UC1.Req010 UC3.Req08 Integrate the application with other systems (e.g. forecasting, image analysis programs)</p>	<p>OSCAR Manager</p>	<p>All app features should be possible to be retrieved via APIs that are well documented.</p> <p>The prediction service is easily deployable either in the AI4EOSC platform or on-premises</p>
<p>UC2.Req14 Capture (plant) images via mobile device app</p>	<p>OSCAR Manager, FaaS Supervisor</p>	<p>Photos are checked for quality (e.g. size, resolution) to ensure that predefined criteria are met.</p> <p>Time of image processing is short, best in real time.</p> <p>Use of existing system / application, especially use the existing data; system should have additional functionality not dedicated applications.</p>
<p>UC3.Req06 Add a user-friendly GUI for my application to ease access for non-IT persons</p>	<p>OSCAR Manager</p>	<p>The model developer has an option to add in a simple way a GUI to the application, e.g. based on the Gradio framework</p>

Table 4: AI4EOSC-1 Roadmap: AI-as-a-Service requirements coverage.

The following developments are planned to be achieved for the first release (AI4EOSC 1), linked to the main underlying components of the OSCAR platform.

2.1. OSCAR Manager

Improved Docker image handling for reduced cold start

We plan to implement strategies to pre-pull the Docker images across all the nodes of a cluster if the user indicates so at deployment time of the OSCAR service to reduce the latency for the initial invocations.

Support for Synchronous Invocations in the Web-based UI

For short-lived inference requests, OSCAR provides a viable solution via Knative. This is supported in the API (`/run/{serviceName}`) as well as via the CLI. However, the web-based UI does not provide this support. This is convenient for users that want to provide quick input to a newly deployed OSCAR service for testing before triggering the service asynchronously for a more scalable inference.

Easy-to-use User Interfaces Specific for inference of a particular AI/ML model

This requirement is expressed in UC3.Req06, where the model developer needs options to add in a simple way a GUI to the application, e.g. based on the Gradio framework. We will provide connectors from Gradio [38] (or similar tools such as Voilà [50]) into OSCAR services so that creating customized UIs for the models in the AI4EOSC Dashboard is simplified to the extent that is possible. This will not preclude from using the existing invocation mechanisms

A JavaScript client-side Library for the OSCAR Manager

With the advent of the JAMStack [51] development pattern for web-based applications, in which the client-side logic is implemented in JavaScript, it is important to create a JavaScript client library to support the lifecycle management of OSCAR services from this kind of pages. This would facilitate the integration of the DEEP Open Catalog with an OSCAR cluster to deploy OSCAR services from the portal itself.

2.2. FaaS supervisor

Support for NextCloud

We plan to extend the support in the FaaS supervisor to allow using NextCloud [52] as an external storage provider to save the results of the AI/ML inference performed out of the pre-trained models that have been deployed in an OSCAR cluster. An initial support to WebDAV [53] was initiated as the underlying protocol, which may be beneficial to achieve this support.

Support for optional data stage in

To support in-memory processing out of a stream of data from the object storage, or delegate into an external workflow management system, we will modify the definition of an OSCAR service and the implementation of the FaaS supervisor to provide this support, thus using OSCAR only to detect when a file is uploaded to the object storage.

3. AI4EOSC Training Roadmap

In the first phase of the AI4EOSC platform release, some improvements will be carried out to remove the legacy dependencies and issues from the DEEP platform. In addition, an interactive development environment will be further advanced for the development of user applications and services.

Requirement	Component	Description
UC1.Req001 UC2.Req04 UC3.Req04 Provision/customize the required computing resources to optimize the AI/ML/DL training process	Workload Management System (WMS)	The WMS provisions while the Dashboard enables customization.
UC1.Req003 Optimize data pipeline for a fast preprocessing data operation UC2.Req05 Preprocess and prepare input data sets to be used for training and evaluation	Workload Management System	Provision as many resources as needed to make this possible
UC1.Req005 Develop the AI/ML/DL model using code versioning framework	Interactive Development Environment	Code versioning is available by using git.
UC1.Req011 Extend existing service features/functionality	All	The use of the platform for model development as well as data ingestion will be friendly for the users(e.g. using interactive environment development). The available services will be extended by including different frameworks and tools in order to deploy advanced models and visualization.

<p>UC1.Req012 Data acquired from meteorological radars have to be transferred to a cloud storage</p> <p>UC2.Req01 UC3.Req01 Store and share raw image data to be processed and prepared for a testing dataset</p> <p>UC3.Req03 Collect and store thermal images</p>	Storage	Storage is provided via Nextcloud so that users can upload their datasets for training, and synchronization with deployments is done using <i>rclone</i> , which allows to integrate with external storage (eg. S3, Openstack Swift, Drive, Dropbox). Further solutions will be considered in the course of the project depending on the user feedback
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Table 5: AI4EOSC-1 Roadmap: Training requirements coverage.

3.1 Workload Management System

Migration from Apache Mesos to Nomad

The current cluster manager in DEEP-HDC is based on Apache Mesos [39] in order to schedule the resources requested by the user applications. Mesos encapsulates the applications in a Docker container, which finally runs on the service clients. The AI4EOSC Workload Manager will follow the same workflow as Mesos but eliminate all the issues associated with it. Mesos is currently in a deprecated stage, with the last version released in December 2020, and the cluster requires ongoing and laborious maintenance. Furthermore, the plan for the AI4EOSC platform is to move toward more streamlined services.

The first evaluation of different alternatives such as Kubernetes or Nomad gave us the following highlights for choosing Nomad over Kubernetes as the most suitable workload manager:

- Nomad is multi-site, i.e. it can be deployed in a distributed way, connecting different clusters deployed among public clouds or federated resources.
- Nomad provides a lightweight and quick implementation, instead of the cluttered Kubernetes environment.
- Easy integration with other Hashicorp solutions like Vault for the identity management or Consul for multi-cloud discovery.

We already tested the deployment and training of modules from the Marketplace with success in Nomad, both with CPU and GPU resources.

Multi-site deployment of the workload management system

The current implementation of Nomad is integrated with Consul [16] which aims to enable discovery and secure connectivity between an infrastructure and across multi-cloud environments. The main purpose of Consul as a component of the

AI4EOSC component stack, among others, is multi-site application deployment. Note that FL might be challenging not only from the legal and privacy preserving point of view but also from the technical one. In this way, this layer provides the technical “backend” support for the advanced learning scenarios (federated and distributed learning) where the end user is able to train models across multiple datasets without requiring a shared data repository. Finally, Traefik Proxy [17] acts as the load balancer to schedule the job between the cloud providers.

Add the AAI support

As mentioned earlier, Nomad 1.5 (in beta at the time of the writing of this deliverable) has added Single sign-on authentication and OIDC support. As a first approach we will still rely on the Training API for authentication, but will nevertheless explore Nomad AAI in the future.

Encapsulates the Management System in Ansible Roles

The Nomad and Consul Ansible roles are already available, and the data centers are deployed by using these scripts. The Nomad and Ansible UIs are protected by a self generated certificate during the deployment process. There is also a possibility that the communication between Consul nodes can be encrypted as well, but this isn't currently supported. We have created several Ansible roles, namely: Nomad/Consul server and client and also the certificates roles. Later we need to provide also Traefik ansible roles to be inline with the **Multi-site deployment of the workload management system** as well.

3.2. Interactive Development Environment

The Interactive Development Environments are special spaces designed for users that want to work directly in the cloud using the cloud resources, like GPUs.

In the current DEEP setup, those environments are deployed in the Dashboard just as standard modules, from a set of prepared Docker images. They give users access to a GPU/CPU environment with Jupyterlab where users can develop code.

In AI4EOSC we plan to give limited execution time in those environments (similar to Google Colab). This will make the use of resources more efficient and easier for users to play with the platform without worrying about consuming too many resources, as we could configure the persistence of the resources.

In addition, we plan to:

- expand the set of available Docker images for development (more frameworks, more versions per framework);
- enable developing also with Visual Studio Code (similar to Github Spaces), for which we already have an initial version based on code-server [54];
- add support for Weights & Biases [55] (similar to TensorBoard [56]) to track experiments, visualize measurements, and provide collaborative approaches to model building; it is integrated with several popular ML frameworks such

- as Keras, PyTorch, TensorFlow, Fastai, Scikit-Learn as well as tools such as Docker, TensorBoard;
- add support for rendering of live Jupyter notebooks with interactive widgets by using the Voilà [50] framework.

6. AI4EOSC 2 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

This section outlines the implementation plan for the second major release of the software platform, AI4EOSC 2. It includes details on the priorities, requirements coverage, components roadmap, and timeline. This section provides a detailed view of what will be done during the second phase of the implementation and how it will be done.

PRIORITIES

Following the planning of the project, the final second major release AI4EOSC will be published by the end of the project in M33 (May 2025). Minor beta versions of the platform will be released for the testing phase of the use case requirements. The following activities must be defined to complete the AI4EOSC final version in order to achieve the use case requirements described in the AI4EOSC-RequirementsDB [35].

- Each use case should deploy their models and make the processing of the data through the AI4EOSC platform.
- Final implementation and deployment of distributed machine learning architectures, including (but not limited to) the federated learning scheme. Users will be able to make use of this technology in a simple way for their collaborative application in cases where datasets are distributed among several data owners.

REQUIREMENTS COVERAGE

As done for AI4EOSC-1, for a more manageable view, the requirements coverage table has been broken down into sub-tables in the Roadmap sections below.

TIMELINE AI4EOSC 2

This section provides a graphical timeline showing when the WP4 components of the AI4EOSC 2 [M19 - M33] will be implemented. This timeline summarizes the roadmap explained in below sections.

Components / Actions	Months																	
	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
PaaS Orchestrator/improve elastic support	█	█	█	█	█	█	█											
PaaS logging and performance improvements						█	█	█	█	█								
Cloud Provider Ranker/algo tuning						█	█	█										
Federated Service Catalogue/scalability & improvements							█	█	█	█	█	█	█					
Monitoring & Metering/scalability & improvements							█	█	█	█	█	█	█					
Infrastructure Manager FaaS integration	█	█	█	█	█													
Improved WMS Authentication	█	█																
Federated trainings	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█							
Testing stage														█	█			
Evaluation stage																█	█	█

Figure 4: Timeline of actions for the second AI4EOSC release. Green cells indicate the time range from development to deployment. All components will still be maintained and improved after deployment, though not shown in the Table to avoid clutter.

AI4EOSC 2 ROADMAP

1. PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning Roadmap

1.1. PaaS Orchestrator

Improve support for elastic deployments

Being able to manage elastic deployments through the PaaS orchestrator is extremely useful for efficiently utilizing resources. Elastic deployments allow for dynamically adjusting the number of resources allocated to an application based on the demand.

Currently, the support for elastic deployments is based on the use of the CLUES [57] plugin for the Orchestrator. During the DEEP-HDC project the functionality of creating elastic clusters based on Slurm was demonstrated, with nodes distributed across geographically diverse sites. The next step is to make this feature more robust and extend it to support Nomad clusters.

Improve support for infrastructure-level operations

Providing administrators with the ability to operate on individual machines through the PaaS Orchestrator can be a valuable feature as the deployments can be managed more efficiently. This level of control can be important in situations where a VM needs to be restarted or updated, or when individual nodes need to be taken offline for maintenance or troubleshooting. The PaaS Orchestrator will leverage the already available APIs provided by the Infrastructure Manager for executing operations on the individual virtual machines.

Improve logging and error messages

Improving logging and error messages will make it easier for developers to troubleshoot and diagnose issues. By standardizing error reporting, enhancing error messages, and updating the logging mechanism, the platform will be more robust and user-friendly.

Improve the deployment workflow performance

We will analyze the workflow in order to identify bottlenecks, areas for optimization and any other issues that may impact performance. We will then optimize the workflow, ensuring that the process is efficient, reliable and scalable.

Implement recipes for automated deployment

We will develop recipes for making the process of deploying the Orchestrator service automatic or semi-automatic. In particular, we will provide templates for running the service on a Kubernetes cluster.

1.2. Infrastructure Manager

AWS Lambda support

This new functionality will enable the IM to directly interact with the AWS Lambda service to create FaaS functions. The definition will be (almost) the same used to define OSCAR services, but it will be translated into an AWS Lambda function with the same behavior, thus enabling the users to use FaaS functions directly in a cloud public provider.

1.3. Federated Service Catalogue

Role-based authorization

Implementing a role-based authorization system can help to ensure that only authorized users have access to service configurations and relationships. This involves defining roles and permissions, and mapping them to specific users or groups. When a user tries to access a service configuration or relationship, the system checks their role and permissions to determine if they are authorized to perform the requested action. This can help prevent unauthorized access and ensure the security of the stored data.

Improve scalability

We will improve the scalability of the system in order to handle an increasing amount of data without compromising performance.

Recipe development for Automated Deployment

We will create a set of instructions or scripts that specify how the service should be deployed in a specific environment. These recipes will automate the deployment process, which can save time and reduce the risk of human error.

Developing recipes for automatic or semi-automatic deployment, including the option for deployment on Kubernetes, can help streamline the deployment process and ensure that services are deployed consistently and reliably.

1.4. Monitoring & Metering System

Authentication and Authorization

To secure the APIs, we will implement authentication and authorization mechanisms that ensure only authorized users can access the metrics. This can be done using standard authentication mechanisms like OAuth2, which can provide secure access to the APIs.

Implement alerting

Alerting mechanisms will be implemented to notify the system administrators of any issues. This can be done using tools like Prometheus and Alertmanager, which can monitor the health of the services and send alerts when certain thresholds are exceeded.

Improve scalability

Scalability is a critical aspect of any monitoring system. For the second release of AI4EOSC we will address how to handle large volumes of metrics data, monitor a growing number of targets, and ensure that the system remains performant and reliable over time.

Recipe development for Automated Deployment

We'll create a set of instructions or scripts to automate the service deployment, minimizing the risk of human error and saving time. Our recipe development will also include options for automatic or semi-automatic deployment, as well as deployment on Kubernetes, which will streamline the deployment process and ensure consistent and reliable service deployment

1.5. Cloud Provider Ranker

Algorithm fine-tuning

By fine-tuning the ranking algorithm, it may be possible to better match user requirements to cloud providers, resulting in more optimal and efficient cloud service selection.

2. AI as a Service Roadmap

The AI4EOSC 1 release provided the required developments in OSCAR in order to support the more advanced features that are planned for the AI4EOSC 2 release, which provides added value functionality to support the requirements identified from the use cases related to AI/ML model inference and the usage of composite AI for improved decision-making.

These are the developments that are initially planned for the AIEOSC 2 release.

2.1. OSCAR Manager

CD Pipelines for Automated AI/ML Model Upgrade for Inference

Automated model deployment is expressed in requirement UC2.E02.US06 where the model developer wants to deploy a verified model for inference in order to upgrade a service with a more advanced AI model. This will require adopting CD (Continuous Delivery) tools such as Flux [58], an open-source tool recently graduated in the CNCF (Cloud Native Computing Foundation) for keeping Kubernetes clusters synchronized with sources of configuration (like Git repositories), and automating updates to configuration when there is new code to deploy. This aligns with the GitOps trend in DevOps, where Git is used as source of truth and when the model is updated, this triggers the re-deployment of the model in the inference server to provide the updated functionality.

2.2. FaaS supervisor

Support for additional input and output storage back-ends, depending on the project's needs to support the use cases.

3. AI4EOSC Training Roadmap

Requirement	Component	Description
UC1.Req009 Try different AI techniques to improve the model performance metrics (e.g. accuracy)	Federated Training service	Users will be able to try Federated Training for their usecases to see if it brings additional performance gains.
UC3.Req10 Train a model using FL approach	Workload Management System Federated Training service	Users will be able to train models in a distributed manner in the case where the datasets to be used belong to different "clients" or data owners. In the case of the federated learning architecture, each data owner participating in the training will act as a client, and a central server will be in charge of orchestrating the architecture. In this way, the server will receive the models trained on the data from each of the clients and aggregate them to obtain a global model

		that will be distributed back to each client.
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Table 6: AI4EOSC-2 roadmap: Training requirements coverage.

3.1. Workload Management System

Improved authentication, authorization and access control

In the AI4EOSC 1 platform, we are planning to implement a basic mechanism for authentication and authorization. Each user is able to manage only his own deployments and should not interfere with others. For the AI4EOSC 2 platform, we will improve the AAA mechanism (authentication, authorization and access control) to provide better collaboration between users. Users in the same VO should be able to collaborate with each other by sharing data, deployments and results via the WMS. For security reasons, users in different VOs should be isolated via different namespaces.

Improve resource provisioning

In AI4EOSC 2 platform, users should be able to bring their own resources and integrate to the workload management system, or create their own instance of the workload management system on their target cloud, either on premises or on public cloud provider. A set of automation tools will be created for simplifying the resource provisioning and integration.

Improved workload management

The AI4EOSC 2 platform will have more advanced features for workload management. Support for job priority and preemption should be added to the platform in the second release. Elasticity should be implemented for scaling the workload execution cluster according to the actual load, adding and removing worker nodes to/from the cluster when needed for better resource efficiency and user experiences.

Add federated learning computing environment

For this task, a central server will be in charge of orchestrating the training as well as communicating with the clients, indicating to them the initial model to be trained (predefined by the user), and subsequently receiving the weights that define in each case the trained model. The server will select the data owners that will participate in the training. Each of them may have a different resource capacity in terms of CPUs and GPUs. AI4EOSC will have an infrastructure that allows to coordinate the communication between server and clients, as well as to train the learning models in each of the clients in a simple and easily scalable way for the user. After consensus is established, a user will be able to act as a server and communicate with the different clients (data owners) that will perform the training. In order to address this functionality, we are currently evaluating tools such as Consul and Nomad to deploy the FL framework on the different clients of the cluster. This should be analyzed in depth in advance of the upcoming releases.

3.2. Interactive Development Environment

We will keep improving the outputs of AI4EOSC 1 for this component.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The present document serves as a supplement to the architecture specification outlined in deliverable D3.2, "*Initial High-level architecture specification*". D3.2 provides a detailed overview of the various components of the platform and state-of-the-art information regarding relevant technologies, including ML/DL, FL, and MLOps frameworks. The implementation plan detailed in this document pertains specifically to the components slated for implementation and delivery in Work Package 4. The plan serves as a guide for developers to ensure that the project objectives are met on time and for users, indicating when services will be implemented or requirements met.

In the first release of AI4EOSC, the goal is to eliminate dependencies inherited from the DEEP-HDC project by transitioning the existing stack to the new architecture. The second release is centered around adding new platform features, with a particular emphasis on distributed machine learning techniques like federated learning, among other enhancements.

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